

Improving Crop Productivity Using Modern Biotechnology Methods

Dev Mani Pandey*

Department of Biotechnology, Birla institute of Technology.

*Corresponding author: Dev Mani Pandey,
Department of Biotechnology, Birla institute of Technology.
Mesra, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India.
E-mail: dmpandey@bitmesra.ac.in

Received: December 26, 2013; Accepted: December 28, 2013; Published: December 30, 2013.

In current situation where dramatic changes in the environmental conditions are very common finding the alternate options in increasing crop productivity is main area that needs to be emphasized to feed the overwhelming populations and ensure their food security. Among environmental conditions like various biotic and abiotic stresses are playing major role in decreasing crop productivity. Efforts are being made to develop the strategies to cope up these problems. To initiate these current advanced biotechnological approaches, tools and techniques are playing very much important role. With these researchers are able to sequence the whole genome of various crops. Using various bioinformatics and other computational tools these sequences are being annotated to bring them in the meaningful form and tell the presence of various genes, proteins and their structures. Recently a genome of the domesticated crop plant sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*) has been reported [1]. It is also possible to compare homologous plant genes [2]. On the basis of gene structure it is easy to find out the number of genes that have single exon only (i.e. single exon genes) and are not interrupted by introns [3]. It is also important to see the presence of single exon genes and their role in the said genome. To find the number of Transcription Factors and their role in the said genome is also important [4].

During the set of unfavorable condition like any biotic and abiotic stresses on a crop at any point of time during their life cycle results differential expression of various genes. This differential expression analysis can be analyzed using various modern biotechnological approaches like Reverse Transcription-PCR, Real Time RT-PCR and Microarray etc. Using microarray data and recent computational approaches now it is very easy to find out the various genes that have been up-regulated by a certain factor (up-regulated genes) and down-regulated by same or other factor (down-regulated genes) while other remaining genes that come in between these conditions (Unchanged genes). Expression of these genes might again be checked for validation using molecular biology techniques. Further, promoter regions of all up-regulated genes, down-regulated and unchanged changed might be retrieved to find the motifs/consensus motifs [5].

These motifs are playing important role by interacting with various Transcription Factors and thereby regulation of genes. Once motifs/consensus motifs have been identified by in silico study, their presence can also checked by sequence specific molecular biology technique like Molecular Beacon Probe based Real-Time PCR [6]. Due to development of recent sophisticated computation tools it is easy to see the protein – DNA interactions as well. Since interaction of promoter motifs and Transcription factors are playing important role in the gene regulation. Therefore, 3D structure of sequence having promoter motif as well as 3D structure of Transcription Factor protein (if not available in the various databases) can be developed using various bioinformatics tools. Subsequently, the interaction of protein with motif might be studied through online server. This Protein-DNA interaction will suggest about the binding affinity of Transcription Factor protein towards motif present in the promoter region of the said gene [7].

Microarray based gene expression studies are already being conducted to find out the detailed responses of various genes present in whole genome sequenced crop [8]. Many crops are also in pipe line for which whole genome sequencing is under processes. Due to development of Next Generation Sequencing Platform whole genome sequencing and gene annotation is faster compared to characterization of gene responses and their involvement in particular function. Plant Transcription Factor Database and Rice Oligo Array Database have been developed and are publically available for scientific community. However, there are still some Transcription Factor genes in rice genome which are least studied about their detailed responses to various environmental stresses and involvement in gene regulation [9]. Therefore, efforts towards expression of these Transcription Factors and their involvement in gene regulation and co-expression networking need to be carried out [10].

Finding the genes that are co-expressed in different tissues and different environmental condition is very much important because they might have coordinated role in similar biological processes. Genes having correlated expression patterns can be best identified by applying co-expression network analysis using transcriptome data.

Subsequently, highly coordinated genes can be further subjected to module identification in the co-expression network. Depending on the topological properties various hub genes can also be identified. Motif enrichment analysis can also be performed to find the cis-elements in the promoters of coordinately expressed genes. This will suggest about stress mediated up-regulated gene expression that is being coordinated through different pathways in the said crop [11].

Some of the differentially expressed and validated genes might be further checked about their spatial and temporal expression using susceptible as well as tolerance cultivars. Once the importance of genes has been established this might be again used to develop the knock-down and silence lines using molecular biology approaches like RNAi etc. These control and mutant lines might be further used to see the involvement of this gene in morphological, physiological, biochemical and molecular changes as well as various metabolic pathways using modern biotechnological, bioinformatics, systems biology approaches. Once novelty of gene is confirmed this can be used to develop the transgenic/genetically modified crops using recent molecular biology, genetic engineering and functional genomics approaches. Genetically modified crops are subjected to several locations for checking their performance and final yield. It's positive and negative impact on human, environment as well as on society is also assessed before releasing to the farmers.

Worldwide eminent scientists working in reputed laboratories are using different approaches to minimize the losses imposed by biotic and abiotic stresses and increase the yield. International collaborations like CGIAR Consortium of International Agricultural Research Centers has also been set up that have key mandate to reduce the rural poverty, increasing food security, improving human health and nutrition, and ensuring more sustainable management of natural resources. In this aspect, a main rice quantitative-trait locus Submergence 1 (Sub1) from FR13A-derived breeding line has been identified that confers tolerance of submergence for about 2 weeks. Within the sequenced Sub1 locus three putative ethylene-responsive transcription factor (ERF) genes were identified and designated SUB1A, SUB1B, and SUB1C. Among these three ERFs, SUB1A is responsible for conferring submergence tolerance to rice [12, 13]. Using marker-assisted selection approach Sub1-introgression lines have been developed and being used as tolerant rice cultivar under submergence affected areas in the many regions of the world giving comparatively better yield. Molecular marker survey of SUB1A and its temporal and spatial expression analyses in nodes and internodes has also been reported [14].

REFERENCES:

1. Dohm J. C., Minoche A. E., Holtgräwe D., Capella-Gutiérrez S., Zakrzewski F., Tafer H., Rupp O., Sörensen T. R., Stracker R., Reinhardt R., Goesmann A., Kraft T., Schulz B., Stadler P. F., Schmidt T., Gabaldón T., Lehrach H., Weisshaar B., Himmelbauer H. (2013). The genome of the recently domesticated crop plant sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*). *Nature*. doi:10.1038/nature12817.
2. Lyons E., Freeling M. (2008). How to usefully compare homologous plant genes and chromosomes as DNA sequences. *The Plant Journal* 53(4): 661-673.
3. Kumar A., Barik A., Kumari M., Vidyarthi A.S., Pandey D. M. (2011). In silico prediction and identification of anoxia responsive single exon genes and their expressed proteins in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *International Journal of Bioinformatics Research and Applications*. 7(4): 376-389.
4. Itzkovitz S., Tlusty T., Alon U. (2006). Coding limits on the number of transcription factors. *BMC Genomics* 7:239. doi:10.1186/1471-2164-7-239.
5. Kumar A., Smita S., Sahu N., Shankaracharya, Vidyarthi A. S., Pandey D. M. (2009). In Silico analysis of motifs in promoters of differentially expressed genes in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) under anoxia. *International Journal of Bioinformatics Research and Applications*. 5(5): 525-547.
6. Prajapati G.K., Kashyap N., Kumar A., Pandey D.M. (2013). Identification of GCC box in the promoter region of ubiquinol cytochrome C chaperone gene using Molecular Beacon probe and its in silico protein-DNA interaction study in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *International Journal of Computational Bioinformatics and InSilico Modeling*. 2: 213-222.
7. Pandey D. M., Kumar A. (2013). 3D structure prediction and protein-DNA interaction of CCCH-type zinc finger transcription factor gene in Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *International Journal of Computational Bioinformatics and In Silico Modeling*. 2(2): 94-103.
8. Pandey D.M., Kim S.-R. (2012). Identification and expression analysis of hypoxia stress inducible CCCH-type zinc finger protein genes in rice. *Journal of Plant Biology*. 55:489-497.
9. Kumari A., Kumar A., Pandey D.M. (2013). In silico analysis of some least studied transcription factors/regulators in rice during abiotic stress. *International Journal of Computational Bioinformatics and In Silico Modeling* 2(1): 72-80.
10. Kumari A., Pandey D.M. (2013) Differential gene expression analysis of some least studied transcription factors/regulators in rice during abiotic stresses. *International Journal of Advanced Research*. 1(8): 412-422.
11. Smita S., Katiyar A., Pandey D.M., Chinnusamy V., Archak S., Bansal K.C. (2013). Identification of conserved drought stress responsive gene-network across tissues and developmental stages in rice. *Bioinformation*. 9(2): 072-078.
12. Xu K., Xu X., Fukao T., Canlas P., Maghirang-Rodriguez R., Heuer S., Ismail A. M., Bailey Serres J., Ronald P. C., Mackill D. J. (2006). Sub1A is an ethylene-responsive-factor-like gene that confers submergence tolerance to rice. *Nature*. 442:705-708.
13. Bailey-Serres J., Fukao T., Ronald P., Ismail A., Heuer S., Mackill D. (2010). Submergence tolerant rice: SUB1's journey from landrace to modern cultivar. *Rice*. 3:138-147. DOI 10.1007/s12284-010-9048-5.
14. Singh N., Dang T. T. M., Vergara G.V., Pandey D. M., Sanchez D., Neeraja C. N., Septiningsih E.M., Mendioro M., Tecson-Mendoza E. M., Ismail A.M., Mackill D. J., Heuer S. (2010). Screening for novel sources of

submergence tolerance using gene-based Sub1 molecular markers. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*.121: 1441-1453.

Dr. Dev Mani Pandey is Associate Professor at the Department of Biotechnology, Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India. He holds Ph. D. in Plant Physiology and Biochemistry from Chaudhary Charan Singh, Haryana Agriculture University, Hisar, India. He was a Post-Doctoral Fellow in various laboratories in South Korea and worked on Plant Molecular Biology and Functional Genomics aspects. He was also invited to serve as

Consultant to Plant Breeding, Genetics and Biotechnology, International Rice Research Institute, Los Banos, Philippines.

Dr. Pandey has presented his research findings in various National and International Symposia, Conferences and Congress as well as organized International Symposium successfully. He has published more than 45 research papers of International repute/peer reviewed journals. He is Principal Investigator of Sponsored projects as well as Guide of many Ph. D. Scholars. His primary areas of scientific expertise include plant molecular biology, rice functional genomics, stress physiology and bioinformatics.